

THE ROLE OF FICTION IN TEACHING UZBEK AND WORLD CHILDREN'S LITERATURE

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Annotation: The role of literature classes in raising the growing young generation to be mature, knowledgeable, ambitious, determined and self-confident in all aspects is incomparable. Students educate themselves meaningfully and morally by mastering the topics given in the textbook. As the head of our state Sh.M. Mirziyoyev said: "Education of young people with high spirituality, modern knowledge and professions, independent opinion in the spirit of national and universal values is one of the most important issues for us" [1.88]. This article will discuss exactly that.

Keywords: literature, independent thinking, logical thinking, didactic, fiction, fantasy, "pattern".

Introduction

For this, it is very important to explain the topics given in the textbook to the students in a simple and fluent way, to familiarize them with the idea of the topic. It is one of the greatest tasks facing our literature today that every read work leaves a deep impression on children, that they can embody the moral qualities put forth in it, the emergence of human feelings, the emergence of creative ideas, the ability to distinguish between good and bad and that they can develop their ability to think independently and logically.

Literature review

Children's literature differs from adult literature by its diversity, simplicity and comprehensibility of image expressions, diversity of events. Our beloved writer Abdulla Qahhor said: "A children's writer should be a jeweler of words" [10.7]. The works recommended for children's reading should be selected correctly from a didactic point of view. The works that can develop the moral-volitional and intellectual potential can be the basis of the child's future success. "The reality reflected in children's literature should be realistic, realistic, suitable for their psyche, mind, understandable and interesting" [2.3].

There is a great need for fantastic works in modern children's literature. In today's rapidly developing information communication, science and globalization period, the role and importance of teaching fantastic works in children's literature

is great. Any work created in the genre of fantasy should create a wide imagination in a child, serve to invite him to creativity, study and research. To do this, we can use fantastic elements in the analysis of works given in literature textbooks or give examples from fantastic works.

Research Methodology

In the 5th grade literature textbook, the fantastic poem "Auto village" by Anvar Obidjon is given for independent study. Each character mentioned in this poem has a fantastic image. It is natural that robots come to the eyes of a child who reads the poem.

Auto village has been built

Our brother Temirjon.

Miraculously,

I have never seen anything like this.

Entering the village

I was very surprised.

Stubborn auto boy

The old auto man said:

-Do not hurry,

Tell your auto dad about the car.

When the mind enters

Pumpkin auto head? [3.250].

Every child is really interested in robots, their movements, controlling them. They begin to analyze their working mechanisms and methods in their own way. It is natural to start preliminary research in them. Inquisitive children, especially boys, will first open up toy cars to learn how they work and how they work. They even begin their initial research by breaking toys. After coming to school, they move away from the world of toys and begin to learn. It is natural that this poem will encourage them to make new discoveries by acquiring their research through knowledge. The teacher can address the students with the following questions while passing this topic:

- Who lives in auto village?
- Can you build such an auto village?
- Can you describe the structure of the old auto man?
- How can the stubborn auto boy's auto head work?
- What actions do you think the auto boy took to throw stones at the auto chicken? Should he have done that?
- What tools do you think the auto cat used to lubricate the auto dog? Could you build such a tool?

- How to make a tail for an auto sheep? Can you try too?
- How to treat the ear of an auto bull? What auto drugs do you recommend?
- What could be the logical continuation of the poem if the ink of the auto-brush had not dried?

Students try to find answers based on their imaginations. At the same time, they try to comment on shapes, objects, metal combinations, colors of objects. When they talk about each image, they try to think about the mechanisms by which they move, about mechanical devices. During the lesson, it is the teacher's duty to be able to listen to the students' opinions, encourage them and give the necessary advice. Pupils also get an understanding of the importance of the subjects they learn in the secondary school. After the analysis of the poem, the students are recommended a work of fiction for independent reading, suitable for the works they are reading. For example, after reading the poem "Auto village", it is natural for children to become more interested in the world of cars. It can be felt that they have a desire to read such works again. You can make them interested in reading fantastic works by telling them about the events of Anvar Obidjon's fantastic story "Golden Hearted Auto boy" dedicated to children. Or it is appropriate to use examples of world literature. At this point, it is appropriate to cite examples from Astrid Lindgren's fantastic fairy tale "Mittivoy and Carlson", which is suitable for this topic. It is natural that especially Carlson, a steam engine with an apparatus installed on his stomach, arouses strong interest in children. In addition, trying to build a car village with students during the lesson will also give good results. For this, we can address children as follows:

- Pupils, let's try to make an auto village model together. Let's think about what tools we need for this.

Students name the tools one by one. Then it asks what forms to use. Pupils use shapes by visualizing each image. Opinions are also exchanged on what material to prepare the representatives of the auto village. Students approach the topic differently based on their worldviews. Here, students are asked about the subjects they have learned about each object, shape, and material they have chosen, and students are explained that each subject and each lesson is important in their lives. Increasing students' interest in fantastic works will help them learn all subjects with interest in the future. They understand that all discoveries and innovations in the world are the product of human labor and effort. Logical thoughts are formed in themselves. They understand that all discoveries in the world are the result of intelligence. They think that the flight of man into space, the discovery of planets, the existence of life on them, the appearance of

spaceships, airplanes, helicopters, and submarines were created due to the needs and fantasy of people.

In addition, during training, it is necessary to give information to students about the genre of fiction. Readers should understand the difference between fiction and fantasy. It is necessary to try to improve the thinking, taste and level of students by teaching fantastic works. Over the years, it has become a habit to introduce students to works of the same format. This caused the student to feel bored with the sameness and to move away from literature and reading. "Any artistic work written for children should be suitable for their age characteristics and levels, should arouse deep thoughts in their hearts, should be rich in bright images and ideas" [4.4]. Therefore, after reading the work, children should be able to create vivid impressions and teach children to be creative and inquisitive.

It is a clear fact that children's writers, literary critics, textbook authors have a great responsibility and task in today's rapidly changing times. Now it is necessary to choose and recommend works suitable for children's interests and dreams so that "literature penetrates into the hearts of young people and settles more deeply" [5.7]. These works should serve to introduce them to the world of spirituality and morality, beauty, goodness, and should serve to form literary and aesthetic taste in them. Fantastic elements can also be used in the reading and analysis of fairy tales given in literature textbooks. So, what is required of a teacher in teaching fiction:

1. The teacher must have read the work to the end;
2. Being able to correctly interpret the fantastic elements in the work;
3. Having knowledge of other subjects such as chemistry, biology, geography, geometry;
4. To be a creative pedagogue;
5. Keeping up with the times;
6. Be aware of scientific research and news;
7. Awareness of information technologies;
8. To be aware of the news in newspapers and magazines;
9. Creativity ability;
10. It requires constant scientific and methodical research.

By teaching students fictional works or using fictional elements in the classroom:

1. To understand that they should master the subjects taught in the general education school;
2. Encouraging innovation;
3. Formation of logical thinking and creativity;
4. Looking to the future with hope;

5. Teaching how to use free time effectively;
6. Improving the ability to study scientific articles or sources;
7. Expanding the world of imagination and outlook;
8. To increase self-confidence
9. Create an opportunity to show individual characteristics;
10. The thought of "I want to know more" is achieved in the child.

At the end of the lesson, you can write an essay or a short story on the topic "I am a future inventor", make things with your own hands, or draw a picture of what you want to create in your imagination. Achieving high efficiency in the processes of mastering the subject of students of general education schools determines the advantage of educational technology: "the purpose of teaching, the content of the educational task, the variety of educational materials, cognitive activity, and the level of mastery depend on the individual characteristics of the student" [8.8] naturally causes various difficulties.

It is appropriate to use the technology of free education in the teaching of fantastic works. In this case, the student can explain his thoughts and opinions about the ongoing process without any "templates", he thinks freely. In this process, the communication between the teacher and students is built on the basis of mutual equality. "The student voluntarily begins to observe the world and people, to study them, to reason, compare, evaluate, draw conclusions based on what he observed" [6.204].

Only when the student begins to think independently and is encouraged during these thoughts will he try to find news and make discoveries. Every opportunity and encouragement given to a child strengthens his self-confidence. "The main basis of pedagogical technology is the teacher. And if we mean that the student depends on the technologies chosen by the teacher to achieve a guaranteed result from the set goal" [7.6], such technologies serve to increase the effectiveness of the lesson and improve the students' thinking skills.

Conclusion and suggestions

In short, everyone has their own talents and abilities. If these abilities are identified in time and directed correctly, a person will be able to make great discoveries. This work should be done from a young age. In this case, teaching fantastic works, holding dialogues in literature classes based on the interests of students will be effective. Choosing and recommending fantastic works suitable for the age and interest of the reader, they serve to increase the incentive to read and educate aesthetic taste.

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